

RADIASIYA TƏHLÜKƏSİZLİYİ PROBLEMLƏRİ: REGIONAL ASPEKTLƏR

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SOLIDIFICATION OF RADIOACTIVE WASTE
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The complex characterization of ceramic paste, which includes a description of its mineralogical, chemical, and thermal properties, was provided in an interdisciplinary approach using thermogravimetric (TG), thermoluminescence (TL), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) [1–3]. The experimental findings shed light on various aspects of the raw ceramic paste sample, including its thermal behavior, composition, and transformation during the firing process.

XRD analysis of ceramic paste reveals that investigated samples contain minerals like quartz, feldspar, and montmorillonite.

The dehydroxylation process of montmorillonite is characterized by distinct peaks in the DTA curves, providing insights into the structural changes taking place. The TL properties of quartz, including TL emission and dose response, are explored, allowing for the estimation of the saturation dose at 13.2 kGy.

These findings contribute to our understanding of the material's properties and behavior, with implications in various fields. The investigation of rehydration in montmorillonite under hydrothermal conditions offers insights into natural clay mineral alterations, which are particularly relevant to the preservation of radioactive waste. Furthermore, the analysis of TL properties in quartz opens avenues for applications in radioactive waste management, as TL can serve as a dosimetric tool to estimate absorbed radiation doses.

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